

**Heterodox theory of the firm
and sustainability –
Concept and application in teaching**

by

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Abstract

The thesis gives an overview of different discussions on economic education and develops possible pathways to improve it by better integrating sustainability issues with the help of heterodox economics in the economic syllabus. The main idea is developed from recognising that for a sustainable survival of humankind, a sustainable economy is needed and that for a change from the current state to a more sustainable economy, education is one of the key drivers.

After recalling major shortcomings of current mainstream economics, the specific incompatibility of mainstream economic education for understanding the pressing challenges of sustainability issues is explained. The work shows with the example of firm behaviour how heterodox economic theories together with findings from business economics instead of neoclassic mainstream theory can not only improve the validity of economic models but also enhance the understanding of the role of firms for sustainable development and the understanding of sustainability as a guiding criterion for firm behaviour. It is demonstrated how new, modern and open-minded economics can constitute a scientific framework for profoundly understanding the situation of impacts driven by economic activity on environment, society and economy. According to the previous findings, a more sustainable economy can only be achieved by an improved scientific framework for the necessary preliminary understanding of the situation and an appropriate economic education that enables the future generations of economic actors such as managers, journalists, and government officials to make informed, normative decisions towards sustainable economic development.

In this spirit, a concrete example of a microeconomic teaching concept for firm theory is sketched as an outlook on how an economic education that incorporates sustainability issues with the help of heterodox economic theories and a change in the economic syllabus in general might be looking. The thesis is a groundwork for a change in economic education and the deliberately chosen conceptual nature and the innovative heterodox approach leaves a great demand for following elaborations of the ideas as well as analyses of existing barriers to change.

Table of contents

List of figures	III
List of tables	III
List of abbreviations	III
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background, problem and research interest	1
1.2 Proceeding and structure of the thesis.....	2
2 Sustainable development and the role of the firm	3
2.1 Sustainable economic development	3
2.2 The role of the firm in sustainable development	6
3 Current economic education and need for change	8
3.1 Significance of education for sustainable development	8
3.2 Current state of economic education, the dominance of neoclassical economics	9
3.3 Consequences of neoclassical economics for sustainability and need for change	12
4 New ideas in economics in the view of sustainable development	17
4.1 General idea of the chapter	17
4.2 Heterodox economic theories and sustainability	17
4.2.1 Unified heterodox economics and heterodox theory of the firm	19
4.2.2 Ecological economics and the firm.....	20
4.2.3 Evolutionary and complexity economics and the firm	23
4.2.4 Feminist economics and the firm	26
4.2.5 Summary of results from heterodox approaches	26
4.3 Business economics and sustainability	28
4.3.1 The natural-resource-based view of the firm	28
4.3.2 Stakeholder theory.....	30
4.3.3 Corporate social responsibility.....	31
4.3.4 Dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity.....	32
4.3.5 Summary of results from business economics theories	33
5 Conceptual ideas for teaching	35
5.1 General aims of a new economic education	35
5.2 Framework for teaching concept and own experiences.....	36
5.3 Conceptual ideas for teaching firm theory.....	38
5.3.1 Part one: What are firms?	38
5.3.2 Part two: What do firms do?	38
5.3.3 Part three: Inside the firm and how firms can act for change.....	40
6 Conclusion	41
7 References	V

List of figures

Figure 4.1: Paradigms in economic discourse (Dobusch and Kapeller 2012, p. 3)	18
Figure 4.2: Domains of ecological economics (Constanza et al. 1991, p. 4).....	20
Figure 4.3: The embedded economic system (Hall et al. 2001, p. 2)	21
Figure 4.4: Firm strategies (Hart 1995, p. 21)	29
Figure 4.5: The stakeholder model (Donaldson and Preston 1995, p. 9).....	30
Figure 4.6: CSR taxonomy (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012, p. 9)	32

List of tables

Table 4.1: Summary of results from heterodox approaches.....	27
Table 4.2: Summary of results from business economics theories.....	34
Table 5.1: Literature on teaching sustainability and heterodox economics	36

List of abbreviations

CSR:	Corporate Social Responsibility
ESD:	Education for Sustainable Development
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
NRBV:	Natural-Resource-Based View
RBV:	Resource-Based View
SSE:	Steady-State Economy
UK:	United Kingdom
UN:	United Nations
US:	United States

1 Introduction

1.1 Background, problem and research interest

Today, humanity is at a crossroads on its development path. Never before in the last 10 000 years of civilisation, the threats have been more globally dangerous for the existence of human-kind and yet never before were the opportunities bigger for a completely new and higher level of prosperity. Human development and accelerating technological progress made life on earth easier and richer. The average life expectancy has doubled since 1800 and the Human Development Index is overall continuously rising (Crafts 1997; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2003). On the other hand, this development brought us to the edge of an abyss. Above all, social inequalities and ecological problems such as accelerating humanmade climate change, a loss in biodiversity and the depletion of natural resources endanger, directly or indirectly, by triggering regional and global conflicts, the persistence of civilisation and its achievements (Schneidewind et al. 2016). Because human development has always been driven by challenges, we, nevertheless, have a good chance that these huge challenges with multiple crises can pave the way for a better, more sustainable, more equal, and more democratic world.

A transition to face the challenges must occur in all dimensions of the human individual life and of the society, comprising a change in values and lifestyles. But since many environmentally relevant actions take place in the economic sphere of the capitalist world, a focus on the way how goods and services are produced, traded, and distributed by firms is necessary. Although there is no business as usual option because the current development with increasing environmental impacts is not future-proof, the changes towards sustainability in the economic system that have taken place until today are small and insufficient, because they focus on modifications of the status quo and avoid seeing the bigger picture of system constraints and growth compulsions. As a transformation of the economic system, whatever it may be, has to come from the people within the system, education is the key. I want to put the focus on three main thoughts of my concern as I think they are the most important means for a change, bringing forward sustainability in the economic system. It is important to first achieve a solid understanding of the economic system and its status quo, second, an understanding of the necessity for a change, and third, an understanding of how change happens. Certainly, appropriate education must begin in school and a lot can be achieved in teaching young people how to behave sustainably for the future of our planet earth. But moreover, since more and more young people study economics and business-related subjects before heading for careers in the business sector, college and university teaching, which shapes how these people think about the economy, appears to be the ideal medium to induce the much-needed impulses into the economic system. This thesis wants to show an approach to a better understanding why this, namely inducing the idea of sustainability into the economic system, can be done via a change in economic education through applying heterodox, non-neoclassical economic approaches in university education in the future.

The master's thesis thus comprises three core topics, heterodox economic theory, sustainability, and teaching. For a better understanding of my approach, I use the example of understanding firm behaviour as it is an important part of the economic system and a main part of microeconomic syllabi to set the frame for showing pathways of possible proceedings.

1.2 Proceeding and structure of the thesis

The concept of this master's thesis proceeds in three steps. It is the aim of the first step (chapter 2 and 3) to build a background understanding of the situation and provide a starting point from which the ideas for the second and third step can be developed. This first step can be understood as an extended introduction to the complex topic as such as well as an attempt to develop a framework for the then following analyses. To begin with, sustainable development, the role of the firm and especially the role of the understanding of the firm as a core element of the capitalist economy in the transformation to a more sustainable society will be considered. After that, the importance of economic education for sustainable development in general will be assessed and the handling of ecology and sustainability related topics in current economic education will be evaluated in order to eventually understand the role of economic education and the need for new ideas.

The second step (chapter 4) of this master's thesis consists of a search for ideas to alter the current economic education. By evaluating specifically heterodox economic theories with a focus on firm behaviour and their connectivity to sustainability and usefulness for economics teaching, an overview is conducted. The analysis focuses on microeconomic theory of the firm, which is meant here as a model for firm behaviour and not like in a large part of the economic literature reduced to Coase's make-or-buy problem.¹ The theories will be analysed with two key questions in mind: First, does the theory pay attention to the sustainability relevance of the firm – and can it be linked to the theory? Second, can it explain sustainable firm behaviour? To do this, the sustainability definition developed in chapter 2.1 will be used.

The third and final step (chapter 5) seeks to design ways to integrate the collected existing knowledge into the practice of teaching economics. Consequently, the purpose of this third step is to conceive, with the findings about sustainable education (chapter 3) and the results from the theory overview (chapter 4), ideas for a teaching concept in the widest sense of the word of an alternative heterodox approach to firm behaviour – in order to achieve the three already mentioned aims. So, education should namely provide first a solid understanding of the economy with the recognition of the impacts of firm behaviour and its major role in sustainable development, second an understanding of the necessity for change, and third an understanding of sustainable actions of firms and how behavioural changes can happen.

The overall aim of the paper is to conceptualise ideas for a teaching concept of an alternative heterodox theory of the firm. Therefore, it is a theoretical paper. After remarks on the role of the firm, on education and on the current state of economic education, as well as the theory overview on alternative thoughts (chapter 2 to 4), the creative part (chapter 5) will be structured as a conceptual study synthesising the different findings. Contents and procedures for a syllabus in elementary economic education on firm behaviour will be derived with the underlying ulterior motive of the thesis to promote a change of syllabi towards a more open-minded education in economics. A final conclusion section (chapter 6) evaluates the procedure and results of the thesis and gives an outlook on further development in the field.

¹ Coase (1937) worked on the question why companies exist if markets are so good at directing resources and when it is better for an organisation to make or buy a good.

2 Sustainable development and the role of the firm

2.1 Sustainable economic development

To this day, no undisputed consistent theoretical foundation of sustainable development exists, because it can be neither derived comprehensively from the edifice of ideas of natural science nor of social science. Yet, the idea of sustainable development represents a caesura in the understanding of human development. This work does not want to assess in depth the meaning of sustainability nor does it want to evaluate the impact and shortcomings of the general concept, but since sustainability is the overall motivation of this project, it is necessary to introduce the term and define briefly how it is used in this thesis.

Although the word sustainability has been used before in different contexts, it got popular and began to have its current meaning from the 1987 Brundtland Report,² that defined: „Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs“ (World Commission for Environment and Development 1987, p. 43). There are many different ways to understand sustainable development, but the universal and most popular idea is that human development has to integrate economic development, social development and environmental protection (the so-called triple bottom line of sustainability, first mentioned by Elkington (1997)). Sustainability in this understanding is the ultimate goal of equilibria between the human sphere and the ecosystem and within the human system and sustainable development the holistic process to this goal (Shaker 2015; Caspari 2004, p. 46). This represents a shift from the traditional dominant view to characterise development with rationalisation in human behaviour (see for example Max Weber (1921)) and the growth of physical wealth to looking at the bigger picture and integrating all effects of development and characterising it in a broader sense, for example as something like growing opportunities of a society (Morris 2011, p. 33).

Many discussions have arisen since then about the notion of sustainability, the meaning of the three dimensions of sustainability and the usefulness of this triple bottom line concept. Conflicts within the concept exist between what is called strong sustainability and weak sustainability concerning the relationships between the dimensions (Grunwald and Kopfmüller 2012, pp. 65–68). The question here is whether it is possible and still sustainable or not to substitute one dimension with another, for example creating huge gains in economic – or social development with a small loss of environmental resources or if primacy of the ecological sphere is necessary (Pearce 1993, pp. 15–17). Other authors postulate an integrative approach where different dimensions exist, but these cannot be seen separated because they interact with each other. In this view, transversal objectives have to be defined such as the continued existence of the human race or preservation of its opportunities to act (Foxon et al. 2012; Grunwald and Kopfmüller 2012, p. 53). Sustainability then always incorporates a notion of justice; justice between economy and ecology, between poor and rich, between men and women, between different people, between the North and the South and between different generations. Sustainable development is

² Details about the report “Our Common Future” (Brundtland Report), released in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development can be found at Huetting (1990).

in this justice-guided understanding based on two foundations: distributive justice today and responsibility for future generations (Grunwald and Kopfmüller 2012, p. 7).

Despite the shortcomings of the oversimplifying triple bottom line concept it will be used in the following as a frame for developing an understanding of sustainability that is structured around the three dimensions. The question is now: what do the above-mentioned ideas mean for the economic system? What could sustainable economic development be? Following the given definitions, it is a development of the economic system, which improves at least one aspect of sustainability without harming any other aspect or at least not harming it too much if only a weak concept of sustainability is applied – while all three dimensions are highly interdependent.

The ecological dimension of the sustainability goal seems to be the easiest one to define and is often understood as conservation of nature and ecosystems – or from an anthropocentric perspective, at least conserving the parts that seem important for humans. Therefore, management rules for using natural resources and influencing the environment can be derived, such as to conserve the natural capital stock or at least the value of it. Or more specific, the use of renewable resources must not exceed the reproduction rate and non-renewable resources must be replaced by renewables. Nor should emissions exceed the assimilation capacity of the natural ecosystems (Pearce and Turner 1990). With all these rules and this specific understanding of ecological sustainability, two problems arise: first, the operationalisation and second, the static worldview. First, it is difficult to measure natural stock and to decide how important each resource is and especially will be in the future. Second, the underlying complexity of ecosystems is neglected by using the idea of unitary natural capital. This thinking assumes that one kind of natural capital can be substituted by another and, moreover, internal dynamics and interdependencies between ecosystems and resources are not adequately taken into account. Finally, all human activity is intervening with the natural ecosystems and influencing them, no matter how careful it is done. Therefore, strictly speaking, there cannot be absolute sustainability because human activity will always use resources and produce residues, and no one knows how these changes in nature will affect the lives of the following generations. In order to tackle these problems, a different understanding of sustainability postulates stability instead of unrealistic conservation. Sustainable development in this view means preserving the resilience of ecosystems, acknowledging that they are not static but react and adjust to human activity (Foxon et al. 2012; Beckenbach 2001). Following this thought, this thesis understands the ecological dimension of sustainability as to preserve and stabilise the existence and features of ecosystems and environmental functions and as the “ability of a (ecological) system to maintain specific order characteristics despite external influences” (Beckenbach 2001, p. 151).

The particular economic dimension of sustainability can at first be understood as the robustness of the economy regarding shocks and crises in general and economic crises in particular (Ötsch and Kapeller 2010). Moreover, concerning the economic dimension, the Brundtland Report still saw sustainable development as growth in physical production and was early criticised for this outdated view (Hueting 1990; Barbier 1987). To this day, there is still a huge debate about what economic development is and how to measure it. Even though, the gross domestic product (GDP) was proven unsuitable for measuring economic prosperity, it is continuously widely used in economics, politics and society all over the world. An overview of the criticism of GDP as an indicator for social welfare and economic progress can be found at van den Bergh (2009). Overviews of alternatives to the GDP as a measurement for added value such as the Human Develop-

ment Index, the Genuine Progress Indicator, the Happy Planet Index, and the Environmentally Corrected GDP can be found at Felice (2016), Schepelmann et al. (2010) and Costanza et al. (2009). Moreover, not only the way of measuring human economic development with the GDP, but also the fundamental underlying idea that growth constitutes economic development is increasingly criticised (Daly 2013). An overview of the debate and degrowth-ideas can be found at Kallis et al. (2012). Understanding and measuring sustainable economic development with GDP-independent indicators is thus only a starting point. A far-reaching and forward-looking understanding of economic sustainability must, for assessing value creation, not be limited to the idea of growth or green growth (decoupling natural resource use and environmental impacts from economic growth) but must be open for new concepts of welfare in a not-growing economy and therefore has to understand existing drivers of growth. Ultimately, sustainable economic development must be the way to a new kind of economy, be it a steady-state or a degrowth economy (Jackson and Senker 2011; Beckenbach et al. 2012; Schneidewind 2012; Schneidewind and Palzkill-Vorbeck 2011). Conceptual ideas for a new economic order can be found at the commons economy (Ostrom 2011) and the debate about a transformative economic science, for example at Pfriem et al. (2017), Paech (2012) and Antes et al. (2012), at the discussions about prosperity without growth and a sufficiency economy (Sachs 2015; Mongsawad 2010; Jackson and Senker 2011) and in movements that are today only utopias like the Economy of the Common Good from Christian Felber (2014).

To operationalise the social dimension of sustainability beyond the notion of intra- and intergenerational justice, several approaches can be found in the literature. Often social sustainability is seen as part of ecological, economic, political or cultural sustainability because social sustainability comprehends all human activities (Magee et al. 2013; Dempsey et al. 2011; Woodcraft et al. 2011). One more specific approach was developed by the Harvard-economist and *Nobel Memorial Prize in Economic Sciences* winner Amartya Sen. In reminiscence to the philosophy of the Enlightenment he postulates freedom as the guiding criteria for human development. He wants to leave means like the GDP as a definition for development and instead concentrates on finding an end or aim for development and thus build an alternative approach to welfare economics. In the so-called capability approach the aim of development and development itself is increasing what individuals are able to do or capable of. It focuses on functional capabilities and substantive freedoms that people value, instead of utility or happiness or access to resources or income as in most economic and social theories. Poverty for example is then understood as a deprivation of capability. Limits to capability can only be overcome by human development and a good development is one that expands the individual capabilities (Sen 1979; Sen 2001; Nussbaum and Sen 1993; Robeyns 2005). In general, the approach emphasises the “importance of freedom of choice, individual heterogeneity and the multidimensional nature of welfare” (Okada 2011, p. 8). The concept was criticised for the absence of an analysis of existing power relations and his pleading for engaging in economic transactions at free markets as the best way to improve freedom, although the general idea of seeing improving capabilities in a wide sense as an end for human development can serve in this thesis for assessing overall social sustainability (Navarro 2000; Fleurbaey 2002; Sandbrook 2000).

Sustainable economic development is consequently to be understood as a way of reorganising the whole process of “social provisioning” (Lee 2012, p. 3) of the economy to make it ecologically more stable and to make it increase individual and societal capabilities now and in the future.

2.2 The role of the firm in sustainable development

In the capitalist market economies of the industrialised as well as the emerging countries, the generation of wealth and the production of goods and services are for the most part carried out by private or government-owned firms. Firms are, in the simplest description, constituted by agreements among individuals on a mutually beneficial order with a set of rules and authority relationships in order to reduce transaction and production costs (Moe 1995). The economic activity in the world occurs mainly within firms, which is why these firms are also physically creating all negative (environmental and social) side effects of the economic system (Shrivastava 1995b). Therefore, a solid understanding of what firms are and how firms behave is a key to understand the impact of the economic system on our world, our society and environment. Moreover, the much-needed transformation of the economic system to a more sustainable one cannot be done without a change in the fundamental behaviour of the firms.

The role of the firm for sustainable development is broadly discussed in academic literature. General impacts and ecological problems caused by organisational activities and ways how firms could reduce these negative impacts in the future are discussed for example by Shrivastava (1995b) and Sarkis (2001), while Ostrom (2012) sees small scale firm actions as a working alternative or complement to a global policy for coping with climate change. Even though numerous books and papers have been written about the relationship between firms and environmental impacts, to a large part the studies are not linked to conceptual reflections about the main drivers for firm behaviour in a capitalist market economy.

Besides understanding the relevance of firms for a sustainable society, it is vital to think about ways how firms can become more sustainable, how they can change to foster sustainable development and moreover, what the triggers are that induce these changes.

Small changes can already be observed. Corporate sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) are central ideas that ask for the responsibility of firms for the environment and for society. Although this is not a new idea, the implementation of CSR-strategies and -measures gets more and more popular and important within bigger companies. The role and possibilities of corporate sustainability and CSR is profoundly discussed for example by Benn et al. (2014) and evaluated by Málovics et al. (2008) who try to link CSR with the concept of strong sustainability. In theory, this means that firms voluntarily change practices to a more sustainable behaviour without governmental regulation. The motivation behind this is that each firm needs a certain acceptance within the society to survive. To keep this societal license to operate the firm has to acknowledge and fulfil its responsibility. This can be a way to trigger a change in firm behaviour from the outside towards a societally desirable behaviour, which can be any kind of a more sustainable behaviour.

The so-called Business Case for Sustainability is a new and popular concept in management and business research positing that firms can improve their financial profit by being more sustainable, through measures to reduce their negative environmental and social impact. It postulates profit-driven development by firms as a way to a more sustainable economy (Salzmann et al. 2005). This concept sees a synergy and not a trade-off between economic, environmental and social aims but unfortunately often reduces sustainability to eco-efficiency. The chances and limits of the Business Case for Sustainability are broadly discussed in scholarly literature (Schaltegger et al. 2012; Dyllick and Hockerts 2002; Salzmann et al. 2005; Whelan and Fink

2016). CSR and the Business Case for Sustainability are certainly not enough, but they are clearly feasible and considerable ways and triggers to make firm behaviour more sustainable.

When looking at the further reaching ideas of sustainability, such as degrowth economy or an economy of the common good, interestingly firms still play a major role. Although these concepts might diametrically contradict with the current capitalist economy, the economy there is still largely constituted by firms (Kallis et al. 2012; Schneidewind and Palzkill-Vorbeck 2011; Felber 2014). Clearly, these firms are different from the current archetype of a firm but still can provide ideas for possible trajectories for changing firm behaviour towards sustainability. Pfriem et al. (2015) discuss the role of transformative firms that can redesign and replace the current economic organisational structure. Moreover, even degrowth or sufficiency has been promoted as a business case to show that a steady-state economy (SSE) or a degrowth economy can actually open up chances for firms (Konzeptwerk Neue Ökonomie e.V. 2013; Schneidewind 2012; Schneidewind and Palzkill-Vorbeck 2011).

Without going into any more detail, the short overview proves that the firm is a core element not only of the current capitalistic economy and must play a key and inevitable role in the necessary transformation to a more sustainable society. Therefore, comprehending the role, structure and relationship of firms to other entities and to the surrounding as well as the behaviour and the change in behaviour of firms is central for thinking about and bringing forward sustainable economic development. All this justifies to evaluate theories of firm behaviour concerning sustainability issues and to concentrate on an understanding of firm behaviour as an essential element of a more open-minded economic syllabus for the endeavour to better integrate sustainability into economic education.

3 Current economic education and need for change

3.1 Significance of education for sustainable development

To set the scene, to understand the possibilities of and demands on an educational concept and to evaluate its potential impact, it is necessary to start up with the idea of education for sustainable development (ESD). The existing literature agrees on the idea, that education is one of the most important triggers for sustainable development, because a more sustainable society is the sum of the behaviour of all its members. Sustainability is not something that just happens or that can be dictated. Because it means a change in individual and societal lifestyle, it can only work if people identify with it. To foster the transition from the abstract terms of science and policy to the reality of life of every human being, the United Nations (UN) declared the years 2005 to 2014 the UN Decade for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) in order “to mobilize the educational resources of the world to help create a more sustainable future in terms of environmental integrity, economic viability and a just society for present and future generations” (UNESCO 2017). Until then, the academic literature focused on static environmental education rather than sustainable development (Bonnett 1999). From the work that was done as part of the UN Decade and the corresponding academic research it becomes evident that without specific education, no sustainability goal can be reached – and that ESD is not just about teaching facts but it requires a new way of teaching (UNESCO 2017; Venkataraman 2009). Various considerations about the challenges to translate ESD into practice and ideas how the educational system can be transformed can also be found in the literature: Venkataraman (2009) discusses the challenges for this translation and the obstacle of traditional educational institutions. Sterling (2001) derives general requirements for sustainable education from case studies of ecological education. A focus on higher education with the general idea that graduates with a sustainable education can lead society on a sustainable pathway can be found at Cortese (2003), Sterling (2004) and Gough and Scott (2007). Up to today, still a lot of research is done in this field from many different perspectives as the recent literature review by Barth and Rieckmann (2016) about the research on higher education for sustainable development shows. There is no doubt that education is one of the most important drivers for sustainable development and a key factor for the transformation of the society into a more sustainable form.

In contrast to sustainable education in general, it is remarkable that there is not much written about sustainable economic education. Some elaborations concerning ecological economic education can be found in the old and ongoing discourse on ecological economics and how to teach it (Costanza 1992, pp. 400–416) but there is no broad discussion on something like Economic Education for Sustainable Development today.³ This obviously represents a significant deficit in research and literature and this thesis aims to, inter alia, show pathways to narrow the research gap.

The focus of this master’s thesis lies on the economic system and the transformation of it (justification for this focus are given in chapter 2). Because education is defined as the key factor for sustainable transformation for all parts of the society (Barth and Rieckmann 2016), it is thus

³ Only a master’s thesis by Parrique (2013) with this title deals with barriers to pluralism and sustainable economic education at the University of Versailles.

also a promising way to convert the economic system into a more sustainable one. To have a direct impact on the economic system, education has to aim at those humans who will constitute and control the economic system in the future. Many of the decision-makers such as managers, business journalists and government officials of tomorrow are economics and business students of today (Ötsch and Kapeller 2010). They will collectively define the form of the economy in the future by applying tomorrow what they learn today. Therefore, it is essential to assess the current state of the economic education at the universities and colleges (chapter 3.2), the shortcomings (chapter 3.3), and to look for ways to improve the economic education regarding sustainability issues (chapter 4 and 5).

3.2 Current state of economic education, the dominance of neoclassical economics

Without giving a comprehensive history of economic thought, it is necessary to mention that the field of economics changed over time and with it the economic education. Since economics has always been a social science dealing with the behaviour of humans and humanmade institutions and entities, there have always been different approaches, theories and schools of thought. With the so-called marginal revolution in the late 19th century, the subject-oriented neoclassical theory of economics was born and got important within the discipline and overcame the classical economics based on the work of for example Adam Smith and David Ricardo. Since the Second World War and especially since the 1980s, neoclassical economics as a metatheory has dominated microeconomics, and together with Neo-Keynesian macroeconomics constitutes the neoclassical synthesis which dominates mainstream economics today (Blaug 1997; Clark 1998; Vroey and Pensieroso 2016; Ötsch and Kapeller 2010).

Although there are deviant branches, Weintraub (2007) defines three main assumptions of neoclassical economics that define the so-called homo oeconomicus: “1. People have rational preferences among outcomes. 2. Individuals maximize utility and firms maximize profits. 3. People act independently on the basis of full and relevant information” (Weintraub 2007, p. 1). Arnsperger and Varoufakis (2006) point out that this definition, which is often used by critics, fits for the neoclassical approach in the 1950s but does not adequately take into account the modern developments within the neoclassical theory and therefore makes it easy for mainstream economists to defend neoclassical economics. The authors, in their endeavour to criticise the neoclassical theory, thus define it with three broader meta-axioms: methodological individualism (explanations are to be found on the individual level), methodological instrumentalism (all human behaviour is maximising the satisfaction of preference) and methodological equilibration (axiomatically establishing an equilibrium state as starting point of all analysis).

In the neoclassical understanding of the economy, some key assumptions and ideas about the firm as an element of microeconomics are elementary. The aim is to scientifically explain and predict the behaviour of private producers of goods and services with a focus on the optimal level of output. From the general assumptions of the neoclassical idea, the assumptions for the firm in neoclassical economics can be derived to summarise the thinking. First, the manager who takes all the decisions is usually also the owner of the firm, there is no separation between ownership and management and therefore no organisational conflicts (which is linked to the methodological individualism). Second, the firm has one single goal: profit maximisation. Third, the goal is reached by applying the marginalist principle as a rule for firm behaviour, which means

that the firm acts exactly in a way where its marginal costs are equivalent to its marginal revenue. Because it is basically a static theory, this short-run optimal production decision leads to long-run profit maximisation. Fourth, the firm acts in a world of equilibrium and certainty (Stubbs and Cocklin 2008). Although some modifications such as imperfect rationality, incomplete information and bounded rationality can be found in modern neoclassical theories, the firm still knows a lot, uncertainty is largely ignored and, most important, a global stable optimum level of output exists for any firm at any time (Dugger 1976; Shapiro 1976; Chand 2016). The firm in neoclassical economics is an ahistorical (formation and change is not regarded), profit maximising, rational entity and the activities are determined by the universal rules of the market, ultimately in order to economise the usage of scarce resources (Jo 2016; Stubbs and Cocklin 2008). It can be summarised that in neoclassical economics the “firm is reduced to the empty box mechanically converting scarce inputs into scarce outputs – that is, its production process and other decision-making processes are removed, and therefore the business enterprise as a real organisation is replaced by a rational individual” (Jo 2016, p. 2).

The beginning of the supremacy of the neoclassical metatheory in economics can be explained, inter alia, with the attempt to legitimise the discipline of economics among the scholarly disciplines by scientificisation or mathematisation of economics in the 20th century. During this technology optimistic time, the exact natural sciences became more and more important and were recognised in society. This phenomenon, also called physics-envy, led to the success of more mathematic, mechanics-like, economic theories that could provide calculated results (Milonakis 2017). These theories represented a solid and modern social-physics-like economics, which boosted the perceived legitimacy and thus importance and role of economics in the society compared to other social sciences. Its results are still today often treated as quasi-natural laws (Weintraub 2007). However, there might be an “ideological function” (Dugger 1976, p. 1) of the neoclassical theory to defend the neoliberal economic order since the Second World War and especially since the 1980s, the discursive power of neoclassicism and the oppression of a pluralist debate with deviant inputs in economics today can be more likely explained in evolutionary terms. A strong path dependency and established practices reward economists whose work is in line with neoclassical theories and lead to a concentration of the research on further elaborating the existing models instead of questioning the fundamental assumptions (Lee 2006; Arnsperger and Varoufakis 2006). There is hardly any discussion about the usefulness of the models and about empirical evidence against them. It is a “particular dynamic within the profession which, operating behind the backs of even neoclassical economists, encourages them to produce all sorts of models [...] but surreptitiously penalises any deviation from, or even explicit discussion of, the meta-axioms” (Arnsperger and Varoufakis 2006, p. 17).

Neoclassical economics is not only the dominant school of thought in microeconomics, but it is the way in which microeconomics is nearly exclusively taught. Although there are other currents in microeconomics (see chapter 4), hardly anything about any other school of thought can be found in economic education today. The vast dominance of neoclassical economics within economics textbooks and their similarity and role in standardising economic education is analysed by Ötsch and Kapeller (2010). Moreover, several studies were conducted in recent years in different countries to analyse the economics curricula on undergraduate level, which are shortly presented to give an overview of the situation. Thornton (2012) analysed the economics curricula in Australian universities from 1980 to 2011. An included survey among Australian econo-

mists from 2011 proved that there was a wish within the profession to update the economic education and to widen what is taught (Economic Society of Australia 2011). Nevertheless, according to Thornton (2012), economic education was not updated with advances in economics and, moreover, became even narrower instead of broader from 1980 to 2011. The French PEPS-Economie Students' Association analysed the economic courses at all French universities. They conclude that the undergraduate curricula at all French universities are predominantly neo-classical, therefore lack pluralism and moreover fail to "develop a critical understanding of both real world economic phenomena and economics as a (fallible) scientific discipline" (The Members of the PEPS-Economie Students' Association 2014, p. 1). A similar analysis for the universities in the United Kingdom (UK) shows that the content of all economic degrees is very similar and that microeconomics is mostly taught by neoclassical mathematical models (Wigstrom 2010). A survey from 2010 among teachers of economic undergraduate course at colleges and universities in Europe and the United States (US) focuses on the changes the financial and economic crisis of 2007–2008 caused in economic curricula. Although more courses on financial topics had been offered, there was, despite the failings of the models, no general intention to change the curricula or the way how economics is taught (Gärtner et al. 2011). For Germany, the EconPlus-Project, a cooperation between Netzwerk Plurale Ökonomik and the University of Kassel, empirically assessed in Germany the criticism that the economic education and the taught theories and methods are one-sided and mainly caught in the neoclassical orbit. Therefore, interviews with instructors from 54 economic degrees at German universities were conducted and the content of the introductory economics courses from these degrees were analysed. The content analysis showed similar to the prior studies that the curricula are narrowed to neoclassical concepts and courses and a broader perspective – such as history of economics, philosophy of science or ethics – is only offered at some universities as elective courses and is not part of the genuine teaching. The interviews showed, most importantly and simplified, that the interviewees confirm the existence of a mainstream that can be defined as neoclassical. Furthermore, half of the teachers see the criticism as mainly justified but there is a gap between the articulated willingness to teach more pluralistically and the realisation, which is explained by given standards about the content and scarce personnel resources (Beckenbach et al. 2016; Fauser and Kaskel 2016).

Unsurprisingly, neoclassical economics also has a huge influence on politics and policy. The work of Grimm et al. (2017) shows for the German-speaking world (Austria, Switzerland and Germany) that the strong neoclassical dominance among economists not only has a huge effect on economic education but also on political decision- and policy-making. The majority of economic policy support organisations (research and consulting) as well as policy involvement institutions (with immediate political operating such as ministries, agencies and think tanks) are ruled by neoclassical mainstream economists. The authors draw a connection between this background and the prevalence of a neoliberal agenda within these institutions. This dominance is presented as a possible contribution to a general revival of conservative neoliberal opinions among politicians and the business elite (Grimm et al. 2017). Undeniably, neoliberalism derives many of its claims such as the deregulation of the private sector, low taxes, free trade and smaller governments from the prescriptions of neoclassical economics of self-regulated and efficient markets. Neoclassical economics is used to legitimise neoliberal ideology in a seemingly scientific way (Bresser-Pereira 2010).

Without going into detail about the relationship between neoclassic and neoliberalism, which is not a part of this thesis, it can be stated that the understanding of the economy and the understanding of the behaviour of firms is today primarily shaped by the neoclassical theory, not only among students but also among professionals in both, the business and the political sector.

3.3 Consequences of neoclassical economics for sustainability and need for change

It is not the aim of this thesis to criticise or evaluate the neoclassical theory. There is a long history of authors who criticised it from numerous perspectives and stances and with various approaches.⁴ Others on the contrary have defended it in the ongoing debate with limitations, modifications and differentiations (examples therefore are concepts such as price rigidity, transaction costs, principal-agent theory or the new behavioural economics) (Keen 2001; Jo 2016; Lee 2005). This chapter wants to dedicatedly point out the consequences a neoclassical understanding of the economy and especially of the firm has for sustainability concerns and what a solely neoclassical economic education means for the understanding of sustainability among students and future professionals.

In 1987, the same year the Brundtland Report was published, Goodland and Ledec (1987) already sketched the incompatibilities between neoclassical understanding of economics and the idea of sustainable development and that the neoclassical theory cannot adequately realise important ecological concerns. This is shown with reference to four different aspects and recently supported for example by Hauff and Jörg (2017). First, the neoclassical theories need defined values for all goods for their models. Because of the impossibility to measure exact economic values of environmental services, these services are systematically underestimated or not regarded at all. This problem amplifies with the degree of intangibility of the service or good as it is the case with biodiversity or climate stability. Their most likely huge (also economic) value for today and future generations can hardly be regarded in the neoclassical models. Second, the phenomenon of irreversible environmental effects cannot be depicted in the mechanistic neoclassic worldview. Third, the usual discounting practice of costs and benefits supports projects with short-term benefits but long-term (environmental) costs. It plays down long-term effects and hinders ambitious sustainable policies. Fourth, the use of GDP as an indicator for economic progress leads to the assumption that growth is always good and to an overexploitation of natural resources and the environment. Moreover, the ongoing economic growth of the industrialised countries can undermine the long-term development in developing countries.⁵ Neither is economic development in industrialised countries compatible with sustainable development, nor can the neoclassical understanding of the economy cope with the demands and questions of sustainable development (Goodland and Ledec 1987; Hauff and Jörg 2017, pp. 118–125).

In general, neoclassical economics reduces the focus of economics to the distribution of wealth by the behaviour of economic actors who experience all benefits and costs. Where this wealth

⁴ Criticism of the neoclassical theory of the firm can be found for example at Sraffa (1926), Marcuzzo and Rosselli (2010), Shapiro (1976), Dugger (1976), Foxon et al. (2012) and Spread (2016).

⁵ Despite the difficulties with the term, it is used in this thesis to distinguish countries with a shorter industrialised history and therefore a lower accumulated environmental impact.

comes from and how it is produced in the material world is mostly neglected, which was not the case for the classical economists such as Smith, Ricardo and Marx, who embraced both, the origin and distribution of wealth (Hall et al. 2001).

Neoclassical economics is, despite its mathematical sophistication, detached from the physical world and the laws of nature. The resulting complications of neoclassical thinking with sustainability demands can be reflected in more detail from a natural science perspective on the neoclassical model. Hall et al. (2001) summarise and substantiate three main shortcomings of this perspective. First and most importantly, neoclassical theories ignore the rules of nature, especially the first and second rule of thermodynamics.⁶ The two laws most importantly say that nothing in the world can happen without the conversion of energy. Every single biological or industrial production therefore needs an energy input, any kind of a perpetuum mobile is impossible. Nevertheless, the plain neoclassical view of the economy is that of a closed stand-alone perpetual motion system with no required inputs or limits. Only capital and labour are needed by the firms to produce goods and services. The only way to integrate natural resources and energy is to regard them as production inputs with a monetary value. The problem with this practice that may seem to work for some resources is that the values are based on current human perception and no one can assume the (especially future) value of the diverse natural resources (except the non-existent perfectly informed and rational homo oeconomicus of neoclassical economics). In short, the ignorance of material and energy stocks and flows in the economic system is what massively limits the value of neoclassical claims. Especially the role of energy, which is increasing and replacing the role of labour, is presented as highly underestimated in current economics.⁷ The material well-being of humankind is not created by labour from nothing, but it is ultimately derived from redirecting energy flows from natural cycles through the anthroposphere. Second, building on this, the boundaries of the economic system that may limit its development are neglected in the neoclassical understanding. In fact, the economy does of course not float in a vacuum, but it is interactingly embedded in an ecosystem (with a biosphere) and a societal system, which is not regarded. Limits to growth are believed to be very distant or non-existent in neoclassical economics. Third, the authors question the scientific validation of the neoclassical theoretical models in general. They provide empirical evidence that these models do not fit to real world economic systems and the conclusions from these models are at best irrelevant and at worst misleading to provide orientation for economic policy, which is backed by other authors (Hall et al. 2001; Stubbs and Cocklin 2008; Keen 2011).

The problems of resource depletion, pollution, climate change, but also unemployment cannot be tackled without recognising the importance of energy as a factor of production that is much more important than the current economic value suggests. A price tag on non-renewable natural resources cannot reflect their actual value today nor in the future. Finally, adopting the neoclassical analyses can lead to serious consequences such as encouraging developing countries to borrow money which causes dependence, and to exploit and sell their natural resources at a cheap price for short time liquidity to pay their debts while the negative side effects are not included in the neoclassical models (Hall et al. 2001). All these shortcomings in the neoclassical

⁶ The relevance and linkability of thermodynamics and the economy is broadly discussed by Georgescu-Roegen (1993); (2014).

⁷ See for the neglected role of energy Keen (2001); Keen (2011)

understanding of the economy lead to underestimating or overlooking the negative externalities (social and environmental costs) caused by economic activities and to a general lack of understanding of the economic-ecological-system (Jaffe et al. 2005; Faber and Frenken 2009).

Since the focus of this thesis lies on the firm, a closer look at the implications of the neoclassical understanding of the firm on environmental and sustainability issues is necessary. As shown, in the denatured view of neoclassical economics, the firm is perceived as above nature. The sole concentration on production and consumption ignores environmental degradation. Neoclassical economists do rarely question the idea of unlimited growth with unlimited production of new goods for unlimited consumption. Moreover, the linkage between environmental degradation, industrial production and unsustainable consumption patterns is not assessed. For the neoclassical firm resources are available and abundant, so the use and exploitation of them is not illegitimate. It ignores possible resource depletion unless it may influence profitability, for example through dwindling resources or an impending price inflation. As planning cycles are usually one to four years, organisations concentrate on short-term financial profits (Constanza et al. 1991; Stubbs and Cocklin 2008). This means that they use straight-line discounting and high discount rates thus preferring exploiting resources rather than preserving them for generations to come (Goodland and Ledec 1987). Economic goals are of primary importance as shareholders' claims are regarded as prior to those of other stakeholders. Inevitably, the neoclassical firm must strive for maximising profits and increasing shareholder value. To achieve these aims and to expand the market share, it has to invest in technological innovation, human, and natural resources, while at the same time it must concentrate on cost reduction to be greatly competitive.

The notion of sustainability is usually seen as connected with a rise of production cost. Installing costly technology to reduce waste and emissions is regarded unessential unless a cost-benefit analysis shows a positive yield through lowering the consumption of costly resources. Furthermore, neoclassical firms can adopt environmentally friendly changes in their self-interest, to achieve organisational legitimacy, to increase profitability through better reputation, if adherence is required by law (compliance), as a reaction to public concern, or through the pressure from stakeholders. A drive for more sustainability comes only from a business case or as an inconvenient obligation if otherwise unavoidable (Bansal and Roth 2000; Banerjee 2001).

As sustainability aspects are hardly integrated in the planning process, it is perceivable that managers regard them as of subordinate importance. The integration of sustainability issues is incorporated in the business strategy level if competitive advantage can be achieved, and also in the functional level if a positive effect in marketing or production is expected. The main focus of environmental strategies lies on pollution prevention or reduction, not on the notion to control pollution or on a potential clean-up. A highly important adjustment factor is at this the pressure through regulations by official directives (Banerjee 2001).

It is thus an established fact that neoclassical firms reduce waste or save resources only if it cuts costs or has a positive influence on the financial bottom line, otherwise dealing with pollution or waste is seen as externalities. Social and environmental costs are imposed on the society as a whole, which means they are not internalised and thus not included in the price of a product. At the same time, economic benefits from sustainable measures are internalised if not prohibited by legislation (Stubbs and Cocklin 2008; McDonough and Braungart 2010).

The responsibility of a firm for a product ends with its sale. Generally, a good is produced for a certain life span, after this the consumer must dump and replace it. Disposal or recycling does not lie in the responsibility of the firm that produced it, and downcycling (the use of end-of-life products to manufacture a new substandard product) is only applied if it promises a certain profit. This linear take-make-waste approach is typically energy and resource intensive and opposes clearly to the circular borrow-use-return idea (McDonough and Braungart 2010). Finally, yet importantly, neoclassical organisations are prone to maintaining an internal hierarchical structure where power and authority remain centred at the top. Employees are considered as resources which can be cut to improve earning power and thus to please shareholders. Environmental aspects as well as social welfare are seen as the responsibility of the government and not of the firm or corporate community (Stubbs and Cocklin 2008).

The pivotal point above all is the focus on the financial situation of the firm. Neoclassical firms and other market actors typically assess its performance through terms like revenue, profits and shareholders-return that should be as high as possible in compliance with legislature. Environmental and social issues thus stay marginal and are only mentioned in annual reviews when it is required by law.

Additionally, any kind of crises do not appear in the equilibrium point thinking of neoclassic models because of efficient self-regulation mechanisms. Thus, mainstream economics is blind for bubble and crises phenomena and harmful economic behaviour.

Although modern economics try to defend the mainstream theories against all kinds of criticisms with modifications of the models, none of these ad-hoc modifications so far fully embraced sustainability because sustainability is just incompatible with the general framework. A discipline of neoclassical environmental economics is growing that takes into account environmental issues, especially resource scarcity, but with neoclassical methods and not changing the general neoclassic understanding of the economy. It is inconsistent because it assumes that the markets are flawed but the firms are still acting perfectly (Gabel and Sinclair-Desgagné 1997). Because it maintains the basic postulates of the neoclassical model, it does not meet the needs of sustainable development (Hussen 2012; Gowdy and Olsen 1994; Illge and Schwarze 2009).

The neoclassical theory inevitably overlooks the role of the natural and human world and thus environmental and social issues. This view hinders the understanding of the field of tension of ecology and social and economic progress and perpetuates the system-induced constraints and not-future-proof status quo. It is therefore unsuitable to provide a framework for sustainable economic development that must fully integrate social and environmental issues into economic thinking. All this shows the contrast between wishful thinking of ecologists and the stylised closed world of neoclassical economics and leads to the definite need to broaden the economic concept to understand and thereby reach the path of sustainable development.

Although, there seems to be indications that the current economic education can make people less caring and can even “breed greed” (Grant 2013, p. 1), there is a shortage of broad research about student perceptions and knowledge of sustainable development in general, about the in-

fluence of education and about differences between different subjects.⁸ Therefore, it cannot be ruled out that economics and business students despite learning solely the neoclassical way of economic thinking and firm behaviour during their studies develop a solid and broad awareness for sustainability, but teaching exclusively neoclassical economics definitely does not promote it.

⁸ Very small surveys among business students can be found for two Australian universities, at Reid et al. (2009) and at Eagle et al. (2015), for an university in New Zealand at Sharma and Kelly (2014), for an university in the UK at Kagawa (2007), one among engineering students in the UK at Azapagic et al. (2005) and one among students from different subjects at a German university at Barth and Timm (2011).

4 New ideas in economics in the view of sustainable development

4.1 General idea of the chapter

The aim of the following review is to collect theories of the firm in heterodox economics and business economics and analyse them regarding their integration of or awareness towards sustainability concerns and linkability to sustainable development. The analysis of the explanatory power of the theories is necessarily twofold. The first question is: does the theory pay attention to the impacts of firms on the sustainability dimensions? The second question is: Can it explain changes in firm behaviour towards sustainability. The findings and working definitions from chapter 2 about sustainability and firm behaviour are used as a framework to evaluate the theories.

4.2 Heterodox economic theories and sustainability

In recent years, amplified by the 2007-2008 financial crisis, a growing desire for alternatives to the mainstream explanations can be seen in the academic discipline of economics. The multiplicity of crisis phenomena related to the economic sector lead to a strengthening of alternative approaches to the pressing challenges (Antes et al. 2012). Students all over the world enlarge their demand for a more pluralistic economic education and scholars are increasingly studying works from outside the neoclassical field and develop new theories (Jo et al. 2017; Davis 2008; Keen 2011; Dürmeier 2005). Especially in the microeconomic analyses of the firm, neoclassical explanations are still very dominant, but much work has been done to criticise the established principles and demonstrate the failures or shortcomings of the neoclassical theory (see chapter 3). An umbrella term for all economic thinking outside the neoclassical theory is heterodox economics as a counterpart to the orthodox mainstream economics and as going beyond it. Non-neoclassical economics however is not a new phenomenon but the history of economic thinking since the hegemony of neoclassical economics is seen by heterodox economists as a bifurcation, as divided into "two incommensurable, alternative theoretical approaches or paradigms, mainstream economics and heterodox economics" (Lee 2008, p. 1). Various schools of thought that emerged and challenged the economic mainstream such as Marxian, social, Keynesian, and post-Keynesian economics as well as institutional, evolutionary, Austrian, feminist, and ecological economics have become known collectively as heterodox economics since the 1990s. All these schools have in common that they stand vis-à-vis neoclassical economics (by presenting an alternative to it or at least criticising it) and that they are typically rejected by mainstream economists (Jo et al. 2017; Lee 2008; Lavoie 2006; Davis 2008). While neoclassical mainstream economics deals with the "rationality-individualism-equilibrium nexus", heterodox economics focuses on the "institutions-history-social structure nexus" (Davis 2008, p. 5). Four key factors were identified as central for the heterodox work by a study among members of the Association for Heterodox Economics: history, uncertainty, power and natural systems (Mearman 2011; Lawson 2005).

Although the different schools are per se distinct, heterodox economics is not just a pluralistic pool of segregated theories, but heterodox economists nowadays integrate and synthesise ideas from all these schools. In fact, some scholars do no longer see defined boundaries but only possibilities for cross-approach engagements and the way to a coherent heterodox economics (Lee

2008; Lavoie 2006). While all heterodox economists can agree on the critiques of mainstream economics and mutually support each other’s arguments, only the rejection of the mainstream is what eventually unites them. There is still a lack of agreement on core concepts or principles beyond pre-existing schools of thought and a long way to go for a comprehensive heterodox theory, while there are nevertheless attempts to do so (Mearman 2011; Lavoie 2006; Jo 2016). There are contentual communalities within heterodox economics that separates them from neo-classical economists but also can serve as a basis for building up alternatives that one day may replace neoclassical economics. Furthermore, heterodox economics is not constituted by criticism, so if mainstream economics suddenly disappeared, heterodox economics would still be there with all its traditions and approaches. Heterodox economics is “not out to reform mainstream economics, rather it is an alternative to mainstream economics” (Lee 2008, p. 8).

A framework on how to understand, organise and work with different heterodox economic theories was developed by Dobusch and Kapeller (2012) who also provide an overview of different heterodox paradigms in the economic discourse that is depicted in Figure 4.1. Mainstream economics fully embrace neoclassical orthodoxy and the by now new behavioural economics, whereas it only very slightly touches the various heterodox ideas.

Figure 4.1: Paradigms in economic discourse (Dobusch and Kapeller 2012, p. 3)

Heterodox economics provide a rich pool of alternative ways of understanding the firm and its environment. Having analysed the many different paradigms collected from Jo et al. (2017), Dobusch and Kapeller (2012), Lee (2008) and Lawson (2005), in the following chapters (4.2.1 – 4.2.5) the four most suitable concepts for the endeavour of this thesis are briefly introduced and the findings concerning the guiding questions of this theory overview are summarised.

4.2.1 Unified heterodox economics and heterodox theory of the firm

The lifework of Frederic Lee, one of the pioneers of heterodox economics, was to build up a complete stand-alone heterodox economic theory that can replace the neoclassical mainstream. In his understanding, heterodox economics is not only a conglomeration of non-mainstream theories, but a new economic approach that can be built up with components from previous schools of thought and new elements (Lee 2008; Lee 2012; Gibbons 2005). Collecting and integrating those elements remains a needed contribution (Parada 2008). Following this endeavour, Erik Dean (2013) and Tae-Hee Jo (2016) each try to build up a distinct heterodox theory of the firm within the heterodox environment of the economy as the social provisioning process. The aim is a more comprehensive heterodox theory instead of one single heterodox approach can offer that explains, “how business enterprises carry out productive activities under capitalism” (Jo 2016, p. 2). The theory emphasises the importance and power of firms in the current and historically grown “corporate capitalism” (Jo 2016, p. 5). Jo adopts the monetary theory of production that was established by Marxian institutionalists and Post-Keynesian economists. He uses the idea of the firm as a going concern that reproduces itself over time and the reproduction of the entire economic system is depending on the reproduction of the firms over long time horizons.⁹ For the second part of the theory, Jo amends the core concept of Marx’s schema of the circuit of capital with a bundle of more detailed schemata for strategic firm decisions such as quantity decision, financing and investment, pricing, production process and sales. The firm is divided into a going plant with the production activities and a going business where all decisions (for plant and enterprise level) are made (Jo 2016).

The theory does not include any link to the environment. Although basic goods or the means of production are the starting point of the explanation of firm behaviour, it is not mentioned where the goods are from. In contrast to the neoclassical theory, firms are embedded in and influenced by a social environment and reciprocally influence the social environment. They are embedded agents and the value and eventually survival of the company is besides physical assets based on goodwill determined by the social environment (Jo 2016). The firm is the source of the surplus needed for the social provisioning process and therefore influences social and economic sustainability, but only in a distant and only in a positive way. The firm as a going concern makes the persistence, viability and will to survive and expand understandable, what constitutes the persistence of the economy as a whole. Firms do not necessarily have to grow, so degrowth does not go against the principles. The highest priority for firms is to survive and if shrinking is the best way, then they will shrink. In fact, it is mentioned that the firm’s production quantity is usually below the production capacity. The stability and going of the economic system can be explained but only of the status quo and not in an integrative sustainable way. Changes in the behaviour only occur to keep the firm going (Jo 2016). The importance of goodwill for the survival of the firm can still be a starting point and explain triggers for behavioural changes in firms, because improving the goodwill can be a motivation for sustainable behaviour.

⁹ Erik Dean (2013) illustrates and elaborates the theory of the firm as a going concern with the case of the US software industry from the 1950s to 1990s.

4.2.2 Ecological economics and the firm

In economics, a unique discipline around sustainability economics emerged and should naturally be involved most with aspects of sustainability. The discipline is divided between neoclassical environmental economics and heterodox ecological economics. Both schools of thought agree on an abstract definition of sustainability that is integratively considering ecological, societal and economic dimensions and on the aim to protect the development potentials of the society. Besides that, there are substantial differences. In chapter 3.3, where the basics of neoclassical environmental economics are sketched, it is shown that they are in line with the neoclassical assumptions and they do not solve the neoclassical insufficiencies concerning sustainability. In the following, the heterodox approach of ecological economics as an own school of economic thought will be assessed.

The ecological economics approach towards sustainability in economics denotes sustainability as non-declining life opportunities. Sustainable development in economics should implicate the preservation of natural resources as well as human resources and the intactness of the environment and technological potentials (Cobb and Daly 1989). The discipline is based on scientific knowledge and understanding of its limitations about the interdependencies and coevolution between the principles and functions of nature and the economy, intertemporally and spatially. It examines the perpetual interrelationship between ecological systems, between economic systems and between ecological and economic systems, recognising the fact that each sector in itself is an extremely complex field and not fully scientifically explored (Constanza et al. 1991). Figure 4.2 gives an overview of the field of work of ecological economics.

Figure 4.2: Domains of ecological economics (Constanza et al. 1991, p. 4)

Hussen (2012) denotes several fundamentals ecological economic theory is based on, as for instance, that the environmental resources are limited and thus scarce, that the biosphere can only survive if the interdependence of the different constituents is recognised and that the idea that the function of the biosphere is only to boost production is dangerously misleading as the economy is also a part of the broader biosphere and as the development of technology restricts itself if it reduces the diversity of the ecological systems or restricts their capability for renewal.

Ecological economists acknowledge that the complexity of the biosphere may make it vulnerable so that small causes may result in great effects. This is why Hussen classifies natural capital in two groups: one part can be substituted by manufactured products, but there is a second part that cannot be replaced, this is the so-called critical natural capital (see debate about strong and weak sustainability in chapter 2.1) (Hussen 2012). The use of a rather strong or rather weak understanding of sustainability is one difference between ecological and neoclassical environmental economics.

The ecological theory accepts the role of technological development as long as it contributes to the reduction of the exhaustion of natural resources but regards manufactured capital as created by natural resources. They can never be fully substituted by manufactured goods, as they are complimentary factors. Moreover, the market is seen as hardly self-regulating when it comes to pricing that should include the shortage of resources and side effects such a pollution and greenhouse gas emissions that cause social costs. Ecological economists propose to adjust price levels of natural resources to meet these negative externalities, such as carbon taxes or cap-and-trade systems, but are at the same time cautiously critical towards pure market solutions replacing command-and-control approaches for environmental problems (Zhang 2013; Stavins 2004).

The main worldview characteristic of ecological economics is, in contrast to neoclassical economics, to treat the economy as a subsystem of the ecosystem of the earth. This means that the economy is dependent on ecosystem services regarding in- and outputs. Figure 4.3 shows a simple extended model of the economic system embedded in the ecosystem with several flows. This model can be a starting point of understanding the interdependentness of the different systems and impacts on each other. However, the representation of nature as a stock that provides a flow of services can be misleading because it underestimates the underlying ecological, economic, and political complexities (see chapter 4.2.3) (Norgaard 2010).

Figure 4.3: The embedded economic system (Hall et al. 2001, p. 2)

This view leads to the understanding that unlimited growth will aggravate the damage of the environment or the loss of natural resources and will inevitably lead to ecological disasters. Ecological economists also oppose the idea of neoclassical economists that economic growth leads to a better social wellbeing, especially in developing countries where inconsiderate treatment of the environment can for example be a cause for droughts and thus even increase poverty despite economic growth (Wada et al. 2013; Dijk et al. 2013). Therefore, it is necessary to move away from the focus on GDP growth (Foxon et al. 2012). It is a truism among most ecological economists that economic growth cannot go on forever as our planet with its biosphere and its resources itself sets boundaries. Implicating these considerations, it becomes obvious that, to conserve natural resources, methods different from those used in the normal market actions are to be developed. Consequence-limiting measures will thus affect the macroeconomic level, as the economy cannot grow beyond the limitations of the regeneration process, nor surpass the limit of the environment to absorb waste.

Moreover, ecological economists have called into question central mainstream economic approaches such as cost-benefit analysis and the separability of economic ideological values from scientific research, arguing that economics is necessarily normative rather than pure positive in the sense of a descriptive science (Victor 2008).

One idea of early ecological economics derived from the finding that constant growth in production is impossible was the steady-state economy (SSE). In fact, the idea has a long history and many economists have thought about it. Prominent contribution can be found at Adam Smith, David Ricardo, John Stuart Mill and John Maynard Keynes (Blaug 1997). The way SSE is discussed today is based on the work of Herman Daly starting in the 1970s and Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen's work on thermodynamic implications for the economic system (Georgescu-Roegen 1993). This SSE comprises a constant stock of physical wealth (capital) and a constant population size with a circular economy with recycling and fuelled by regenerative energy (Daly 1991). It does not only incorporate nature as the biophysical limits, it also includes a moral change in the way that material wealth may someday be surpassed by human aspiration (Hussen 2012). Thus, ecological economics want to postulate that another world is possible but it would look quite different from the current world and clearly, the role of the economy has to be courageously and fundamentally changed (Foxon et al. 2012). In this sense, Keynes warned against overestimating the importance of the ongoing economy and of "sacrificing to its supposed necessities other matters of greater and more permanent significance" (Keynes 1930, p. 373).

Although it seems difficult, transferring the above theoretical thoughts to the entity of the modern firm is not only a utopia but can be seen in the concept of an ecocentric business model. To meet the need for more sustainability, and also reduce production costs, ecocentrically orientated organisations can strive for closed-loop or cradle-to-cradle production systems. This means they can minimise the use of natural resources and energy and are ambitious to strive towards renewing or recycling them, at best in cooperation with like-minded firms. Shrivastava (1995a) characterises ecologically orientated firms as imitating the natural ecosystems by cooperating interactively. By treating nature as a key stakeholder, they aim to minimise environmental damage by sharing their respective infrastructures to foster recycling and renewable energy in a so-called industrial ecosystem.

Another fundamental commitment of an ecocentric and ecologically producing firm is to manufacture eco-friendly goods and at the same time reduce material use altogether. To achieve this aim they cut packaging, use less and renewable energy, reduce the use of natural resources by increasing the use of recycled material and minimise waste and pollution at the same time. Moreover, they internalise the cost of any pollution or waste in their product. Their aim is to prevent waste and pollution altogether to come to a zero-waste production rather than having to control emissions after producing them (end-of-pipe) or making amends through the purchase of carbon credits as compensation after harm is done. An ecocentric firm does not only minimise the use of raw material, but it takes responsibility for the entire life cycle of their products. It rather sells services than products or hires them out to save resources. If end-of-life products are unavoidable they recycle and return them in the production cycle and at best produce same quality products in cooperation within an industrial ecosystem (Shrivastava 1995a).

A rethinking concerning discount rates is proposed in the way that ecocentric firms do not apply traditional discounting models but rather implement hyperbolic discounting where the near future is discounted at a higher rate than the distant future resulting in the effect that cost-benefit calculations would prove highly positive for the environment (Stubbs and Cocklin 2008). In contrast to neoclassical, mostly hierarchical organisation structures, the ecocentric firm has a rather non-hierarchical, flat, decentralised organisation structure with special attention to employee participation on all levels as well as a low salary discrepancy. To balance shareholders' interests against the interests of other stakeholders is their prior aim (Shrivastava 1995a).

To achieve all of that in the current capitalist system, ecological firms must be driven by ethical motives if not forced by law. In theory they then integrate sustainability aims in their company profile and try to improve the wellbeing of all their stakeholders. They focus on long-term perspectives rather than on a short-term profit, not neglecting the awareness that profit has to be generated to invest in their aims.

4.2.3 Evolutionary and complexity economics and the firm

Evolutionary economics represents an understanding of the economy that is inspired by evolutionary biology. It focuses on non-equilibrium processes and the perpetual transformation of the economy. The processes emerge from multilateral actions of various agents with bounded rationality that may learn from experience. The interactions and differences contribute to the change in the economy (Witt 2008; Nelson and Winter 2002).

The term was coined by Thorstein Veblen, who developed, inspired by Darwin's ideas, alternatives to the passive and essentially inert neoclassical economics (Veblen 1898). Joseph Schumpeter's idea of creative destruction that he derived from the work of Karl Marx¹⁰ can be seen in this tradition and as a contribution to the evolutionary understanding of economics. The economic stability is perpetually destroyed by entrepreneurs or firms who try to introduce innovations. A successful, disruptive technology disturbs the economy, because existing technologies and means of production lose their importance within the economy (Schumpeter 2013). A major

¹⁰In Marxian economic theory, the concept refers generally to the linked processes of accumulation and annihilation of wealth (Marx (1963); Marx (1973)).

contribution to the formation of today's evolutionary economics was the work of Richard Nelson and Sidney Winter. In the publication "An Evolutionary Theory of Economic Change" from 1982, the authors develop an alternative to the neoclassical black box model of the firm, transforming inputs in outputs which is represented by a production function. As mentioned in chapter 3, this understanding of the firm neglects uncertainties as well as differences between firms and competitive advantages from technological innovation and consequently all endogenous dynamic within the economy. Based on existing evolutionary economic ideas, the authors sketch a model of firm behaviour (Nelson and Winter 1982). The firms in this model are motivated by profit and continuously trying to improve it, however, their behaviour is not assumed as profit-maximising over a given choice set as assumed in neoclassical models. The analysis does not aim for an industry equilibrium in which all firm are producing at their optimal output level. Not a maximisation calculus is used, but "the firms are modelled as simply having, at any given time, certain capabilities and decision rules" (Nelson and Winter 1982, p. 4). The model represents a small economy with interacting firms and the possibility to improve productivity with technological change within the individual firm. The general economic development is driven by the search process for technological changes within the firms (Nelson and Winter 1982).

Clearly, the understanding of firm behaviour in evolutionary economics differs from other economic branches. Individually different restrictions in information, knowledge, and capabilities play an important role as well as understanding the firm not as one individual but as consisting of different departments.¹¹ These departments can have conflicting interests, and conflicting objectives can exist within a firm. Finally, the firm is not maximising its profit by exploiting the given situation but trying to improve it by exploring new ways of production and organisation.

Because the focus lays on changes and conditions where the structure connecting inputs to outputs is unknown, the methodology in evolutionary economics is based on simulation models such as the Nelson-Winter model or newer model as the model of firms as bargaining agencies by Spread (2016) rather than on formal models as in neoclassical economics. The model of decision-making under bounded rationality from Wall (1993) can be taken as an characteristic example to show that in these models the agents search for satisfying solutions (instead of exploiting the optimum) and how this satisficing behaviour with learning and adaptation can be modulated. This search is first local, because new solutions emerge as marginal modifications of existing routines, second sequential, because alternatives are considered one at a time, and third driven by experience, because learning leads to updating of current routines on the basis of interpretation of previous experience (Wall 1993).

In this understanding, evolutionary economics is related to the newer field of complexity economics that uses computational, procedural rather than mathematical analysis as characteristic to discover mechanisms that create patterns of change in the economic system, "that is not dead, static, timeless, and perfect, but alive, ever-changing, organic, and full of messy vitality" (Arthur 2013). This leads to the idea of the economy as a complex adaptive system.

¹¹ The acceptance of different departments can build a bridge to business theories that examine the processes within specific departments for better understanding firm behaviour, which will be assessed in chapter 4.3.

Sustainable economic development presupposes drastic changes in the economy and it seems obvious that the insights from evolutionary and complexity economics are needed to understand drivers and barriers of change processes in the economy. For the understanding of path dependencies and especially path changing technological innovations that can bring significant environmental relief, these theories are of great help (Nill 2001). The work of Beckenbach (2001) is an example of such an evolutionary model integrating ecological and economic changes and the interactions of both.

The development rate of environmental innovation, technological innovations that contribute to sustainability of the economy, is still insufficiently slow.¹² According to Faber and Frenken (2009), a main reason for this slowness is that neither neoclassical environmental economics nor ecological economics can adequately incorporate these technological change in their frameworks. The authors present an overview of how evolutionary economics can contribute to environmental studies and how it can improve environmental policy-making. They demonstrate how an evolutionary economic framework can, due to recognising uncertainties and the use of scenario and sensitivity analysis, improve the understanding of three major problems with environmental innovations: the double (negative and positive) externality problem, the problem with technological transitions, and the dynamics of consumer demand (Faber and Frenken 2009).

Foxon et al. (2012) argue that complexity economics and heterodox economics in general are necessary to realise the needed changes in the economic system and to form a realistic policy agenda. Understanding the characteristics of complex systems is highly relevant to the study of sustainability that requires analyses of the links and interactions between the economic, ecological and social sphere (Foxon et al. 2012). Complexity economics can, according to Faber and Frenken (2009), thus be used as a new generation of evolutionary economic modelling, combining the evolution of natural systems with technological and institutional¹³ evolution. This can give a picture across micro, meso and macro levels of the coevolution of ecosystems, technologies, institutions as well as business strategies and user practises and the interactions of these different complex systems (Foxon 2011). Agent-based modelling can here be a promising method of modelling parts of the economy to find better answers to economic questions such as innovation behaviour (Beckenbach et al. 2013).

Furthermore, evolutionary and complexity economics allows, in contrast to neoclassical economics, thoughts about moving beyond GDP as a measure of economic growth and even about prosperity without growth and to show how human needs can be satisfied without conventional economic growth or without growth at all (Foxon et al. 2012).

¹² A comprehensive analysis of the problem as a market failure and policy solutions from a neoclassical perspective can be found at Jaffe et al. (2005).

¹³ The heterodox school of thought of institutional economics, a leading heterodox approach to economics focusing on the role of institutions in shaping economic behaviour is not considered in this thesis. For an overview of institutionalism see Hodgson (2004) and for the interplay of institutions and the environment see Vatn (2007).

4.2.4 Feminist economics and the firm

Feminist economics is a critical heterodox current questioning the history, epistemology, and methodology of economic research originating in the attempt to overcome androcentric biases and assessing the social constructions of economics. Feminist economics calls attention to value judgements and so questions the conception of economics as a positive science (Beneria et al. 2011; Power 2004; Ferber and Nelson 2009; Waring and Steinem 1988). Coming from working on traditionally women-relevant topics, it focuses on topics that are ignored by most economists such as care and unpaid work, gender inequalities and intra-household bargaining. Feminist economists demand a more inclusive economics and economy and argue for using new methods such as the capabilities approach (see chapter 2.1) rather than GDP when assessing economic success as well as including ethical judgments. Although, there is to this date no feminist theory of the firm, which is why this chapter is kept short, feminist economics covering welfare economics and labour economics, provides a rich pool of work and ideas concerning the social impacts and thus social sustainability of economic activity as well as new thinking about aims and success of economic activity and thus economic sustainability.

4.2.5 Summary of results from heterodox approaches

Heterodox economic theories are more an ongoing research programme than a completed and established theory. Nevertheless, many insights about sustainability issues can be gathered. All examined heterodox ideas have in common that they see the economy as an open, dynamic system with diverse agents that is embedded in a wider environment with overlapping and interactions. A heterodox framework unifying the analysis of the coevolution of environmental systems, physical and social technologies, and economic (and therefore business) plans, that constitute the creation of wealth in the industrialised countries, can hugely contribute to the understanding of the role of the firm in this process. With the help of the framework from chapter 2, the findings regarding the two guiding questions for this literature review, first whether and how the theory pays attention to the sustainability relevance of the firm and second, whether it can explain sustainable firm behaviour, are summarised in the following table. Overall, the more far-reaching, deeper and sounder findings could be obtained regarding the first question.

	Explanatory power for influence and linkability of firm behaviour on and with sustainability			Triggers for change in firm behaviour
	Ecological Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Economic Sustainability	
Unified heterodox theory of the firm following Jo (2016), Dean (2013) and Lee (2012)	No link to the ecological environment	Firms are understood as embedded in and dependent on the social environment Impact of firms seen as the source of the surplus needed for the social provisioning process	Firm as a going concern makes the persistence, viability and will to survive and/or expand of firms understandable, which constitutes the economy Firms have need to survive but no need to grow	Firms have different goals not only profit maximisation Improving the “goodwill” can be a motivation for sustainable behaviour
The firm in ecological economics	The embeddedness of the firm in the natural environment is the central idea The mutual interaction between firms and ecosystems and ways to reduce negative impacts are assessed	Predominantly looking at inter-generational justice and not at equity within the current generation	Possible limits to growth are considered and growth of the economy is seen as a possible threat Ideas for SSE and industrial ecology show pathways for a new economic sustainability	Firms focus on long-term perspectives rather than on a short-term profit They integrate sustainability aims because of ethical motives and to improve the wellbeing of their stakeholders
The firm in evolutionary and complexity economics	Interaction and coevolution of economic and thus firm behaviour with environmental systems is considered Assessment of obstacles to environmental innovation	Hardly any link between firm behaviour and social sustainability can be drawn	Societal wealth is emerging from firm behaviour Self-interest of firms and will to survive on the agent level can explain growing Assessment of non-equilibrium situations	The notion of a non-equilibrium economy and the focus on change processes can explain how and why firms change their behaviour, what is needed therefore and what impact these changes may have
(The firm in) feminist economics	Not the main focus, but shares many perspectives with ecological economics	Strong focus on wellbeing, capabilities and thus economic effects on social sustainability	Different view on economic success and its aims. Different assessment fits modern economic sustainability definitions	No firm theory but critical assessment of path dependencies from social constructions, gender roles and power relations

Table 4.1: Summary of results from heterodox approaches

4.3 Business economics and sustainability

A main difference between the neoclassical and a heterodox or new way of understanding and teaching the firm can be the rejection of seeing the firm as one entity, as an “empty box mechanically converting scarce inputs into scarce outputs” (Jo 2016, p. 2). Insights into firm behaviour in different departments with their own dynamics can help to better understand the sustainability relevant actions of firms. This closer look at the firm behaviour and the assessment of interactions of different departments with own interests form a major column of evolutionary economics (chapter 4.2.3). Coming from this perspective, literature from business studies can help to gain more insight into the characteristics of these departments as well as into the sustainability-relevant activities and recent developments. Business studies can provide understanding especially about how and why firms may change their behaviour towards sustainability. Traditionally the study of the inner workings of the firm has been largely absent from environmental considerations (Johnstone 2007). Consequently, the definition and understanding of sustainability in business studies was long limited to a narrow financial dimension, to “create long-term shareholder value by embracing the opportunities and managing the risks that result from an organisation’s economic, environmental, and social responsibilities” (Pojasek 2007, p. 1). However, a change in the literature and in practice can be observed and the idea of a societal responsibility of firms gains more and more attention. Already Gabel and Sinclair-Desgagné (1997) for example, after showing the inconsistencies of the neoclassical environmental economic understanding of the firm, sketch a model of the firm to explain why and how firms deviate from the neoclassical expectations and that they can actually find profitable opportunities from strict environmental regulations. Rodriguez et al. (2002) demonstrate positive effects of sustainable development on firms and Schrettle et al. (2014) provide explanations how decisions for sustainability moves of firms are motivated. Consequently, some currents in business research might be very useful for this thesis, which is why in this chapter the heterodox economics approach to firm theory will be extended to promising business economics concepts that are found at the overviewing literature on business sustainability (Wells 2013; Schaltegger et al. 2017; Hitchcock and Willard 2009; DesJardins 2007; Elkington 1997; D’amato et al. 2009).

4.3.1 The natural-resource-based view of the firm

The so-called natural-resource-based view (NRBV) of the firm introduced by Hart (1995) is an extension of the resource-based view (RBV) in business studies arguing that the competitive advantage and uniqueness of a firm is determined by its strategically more valuable internal resources compared to competitors. Both theories highlight the connection between firm resources, capabilities and competitive advantages and propose that firms should look inside the organisation to find and improve the sources of competitive advantage rather than searching for a competitive environment for the firm (Wernerfelt 1984; Peteraf 1993; Barney 2001).¹⁴

¹⁴ There are many analogies between the RBV and the firm in evolutionary economics such as firm heterogeneity and the mechanism that the internal routines of some firms are more effective and efficient than other. See Barney (2001) for a positioning of the RBV relative to evolutionary economics.

In its concentration on the internal resources, the older RBV leaves aside the embeddedness of the firm. The NRBV in contrast understands the resources, capabilities and competitive advantage of a firm as based on the relationship of the firm to the natural environment and the relationship to external stakeholders and considers socioeconomic drivers of poverty and inequality as important impacts. The natural and social environment is seen as both, restriction for business activity and source for competitive advantage (Hart 1995; Hart and Dowell 2011; Hoffmann et al. 2002). This view can help to understand sustainable behaviour of firms because it draws a link between firm behaviour that improves sustainability and the competitive advantage of the firm. Sustainability strategies can hence be the foundation of competitive advantage. In this understanding, three key strategies for firms are developed by Hart (1995), very simply explained in the following and depicted in Figure 4.4.

The first one is called “pollution prevention”, which means to minimise emissions and waste of production instead of end-of-pipe technologies. This lowers environmental impacts and can simultaneously reduce costs due to reduced inputs, simpler processes and lower compliance costs and thus supports competitive advantage.

The second strategy step called “product stewardship” is to minimise the life-cycle costs along the entire value chain of the product system with measures such as smarter product design. With this approach, the firm can even better take care of the environmental impacts of the economic activities. Concurrently, the firm can improve its reputation and legitimacy among all kinds of stakeholders, which is needed to maintain the competitive advantage.

The third and final strategy is called “sustainable development” and means firm strategies beyond greening to include economic and social concerns and to reach an overall (environmentally, economically, and socially) sustainable way of operating. This comprises recognising the link between material consumption in the industrialised countries and environmental impacts in the developing world and thus selling-less strategies as well as initiatives such as building markets in developing countries. A commitment to sustainable development might not enhance short-term profits but can build up a viable business for the long-term future.

Figure 4.4: Firm strategies (Hart 1995, p. 21)

Sustainable firm behaviour, which is characterised here very similar to the ecocentric business model from ecological economics (chapter 4.2.2), can be explained with this concept by assuming that the competitive advantage can be improved with it. This may happen on two levels: first, by improving the internal resources and capabilities (for example cost reductions) and second, by improving the external legitimacy and reputation (see next chapter on stakeholder theory).

In his later work, Hart extended the strategies by splitting the third “sustainable development” strategy into two strategies, one called “clean technology” to highlight the need for innovations of disruptive new technologies and the other called “base of the pyramid” to underline the requirement to meet the needs of the poor, while of course both entail business opportunities (Hart and Dowell 2011).

4.3.2 Stakeholder theory

The stakeholder theory, established by Freeman (1984), assumes that a business is constituted by the relationships among different groups that have a stake in the business activity. The creation of economic value and the competitive advantage of a firm are thus determined by the interaction of stakeholders. For the firm, the core idea of stakeholder theory is that organisations that manage their stakeholder relationships survive longer and perform better than other organisations. In a more general sense, it raises the question of the role of the firm in the modern society.

In a broad definition, which is not shared by every author but seems to be most useful for this work, stakeholders are „any group or individual that can affect or be affected by the realization of an organization’s purpose“ (Freeman 2010, p. 26). As Figure 4.5 shows, this can range from close groups such as shareholders and employees up to more distant groups such as non-governmental organisations.

Figure 4.5: The stakeholder model (Donaldson and Preston 1995, p. 9)

The literature on stakeholder theory works on why firms should consider certain stakeholders and to whom they should pay attention. Therefore, stakeholders can be assigned to different classes according to categories such as power, legitimacy and urgency (Donaldson and Preston 1995; Mitchell et al. 1997). Without going into detail about stakeholder management, it is obvious that his approach can explain changes in firm behaviour. Following the theory, sustainable firm behaviour will occur if sustainability is a major stakeholder interest. Even if the environment is not seen as a stakeholder on its own, environmental as well as social and sustainability issues in general can be brought into the decision-making process of firms through the representation by stakeholders that then can act as intermediaries. To achieve this, according to Hörisch et al. (2014), three major challenges have to be met: first, strengthening the sustainability interests of stakeholders in general, second, creating shared sustainability interests among different stakeholder groups, and third, empowering stakeholders to act as intermediaries for nature and sustainable development. As strategies to meet these challenges, the authors suggest education (knowledge as a key), regulation (strong incentives that encourage stakeholders to cooperate on sustainability), and sustainability value creation (Hörisch et al. 2014). Betts et al. (2015) demonstrate empirically the positive relationship between stakeholder pressure and the implementation of environmental strategies by firms in different industries. It is clear that stakeholder pressure can be a way of influencing firm behaviour and stakeholder theory can be of help to understand this dynamic.

4.3.3 Corporate social responsibility

The debate about corporate social responsibility (CSR) and corporate sustainability is about self-regulating decisions within the strategic management of a firm that are relevant for the environmental and social impact of the firm. Therefore, it aims even more directly than the stakeholder theory not only at the firm's economic interests but also at the responsibility of a firm within the society. Unlike corporate citizenship, it is not about additional activity such as charity engagement, but it means doing the core business in a more responsible way. Mostly CSR means activities of firms that voluntarily go beyond compliance and statutory requirements, which can include activities such as exceling emission standards or providing more detailed sustainability reports (Montiel 2008; Salzmann et al. 2005; Garriga and Mel 2004).

CSR can be a way of how firms can change their image from being the "bad guys, causing environmental disasters, financial scandals, and social ills" to being "the solution of global regulation and public goods problems" (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012, p. 2). Kitzmueller and Shimshack (2012) develop a framework for and an empirical overview of the economic analyses of CSR to examine whether CSR should exist and why it has emerged – because at first sight CSR contradicts with the neoclassical economic proposition that, as Friedman puts it, "the only responsibility of business is to maximize profits" (Friedman 1970). One finding is that even with a neoclassical economic understanding, CSR can be part of an optimal firm strategy, but not-for-profit CSR exists, too. Therefore, the authors developed a taxonomy to distinguish different types of CSR that is illustrated in Figure 4.6.

		Shareholders	
		Social Preferences	Classical Preferences
Stakeholders	Social Preferences	Not for profit CSR Mixed effects on profit	Strategic CSR Profit maximisation
	Classic, monetary preferences	Not for profit CSR Reduction of profits	No CSR Profit maximisation

Figure 4.6: CSR taxonomy (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012, p. 9)

No CSR and strategic CSR are in line with the neoclassical assumption of profit maximisation. Not-for-profit CSR can have positive economic side effects through attraction of employees and customers that value the goals of the firm, or shareholders sustain the cost out of individual motivation (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012). Moreover, the authors found that under certain conditions CSR may produce higher welfare than public provisioning channels, which challenges the traditional view that only the government can correct market failures associated with the provisioning of public goods or positive and negative externalities (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012).

CSR is not a theory on its own to explain firm behaviour, yet it can be useful to understand how firms can act both unanimously with and deviant from profit maximising behaviour when confronted somehow with environmental or social impacts of their behaviour. Especially in combination with stakeholder theory, it can help understanding possible ways and triggers of changing firm behaviour towards sustainability.

4.3.4 Dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity

The ideas of dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity are further developments of the rather static RBV understanding of the firm considering a rapidly and non-linear changing environment which matches in turn the worldview of evolutionary and complexity economics. It builds on the idea that different markets operate at different speeds and focuses on high velocity markets.

Absorptive capacity is “a firm’s ability to recognize the value of new information, assimilate it, and apply it to commercial ends” (Cohen and Levinthal 1990, p. 128). In the idea of dynamic capabilities, not the resources of a firm alone but its meta-competences of integrating, recombining and releasing new capabilities, the ability to continuously alter resources and competences, “the capacity of an organization to purposefully create, extend, or modify its resource base” (Helfat et al. 2007, p. 4) sustain a competitive advantage (Peteraf et al. 2013; Teece et al. 1997; Eisenhardt and Martin 2000).

Various authors have discovered links between dynamic capabilities and sustainability practices meaning that sustainability practices can actually be a way of sustaining the competitive advantage of a firm. Dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity can be concepts to recognise and monitor emerging sustainability concepts from various stakeholders and sustainable development opportunities (Wu et al. 2013). Chakrabarty and Wang (2012) identify research and development intensity, Hofmann et al. (2012) the adoption of advanced technology, experiences with inter-firm relations, and capacity for product innovation as dynamic capabilities that increase sustainability practices of firms. In their characteristic as dynamic capabilities, they also help to sustain competitive advantage. Beske et al. (2014) identify specific dynamic capabilities such as knowledge sharing along the supply chain for managing sustainable supply chains in the food industry.

Just as CSR, absorptive capacity and especially dynamic capabilities are not firm theories, but they can be concepts to comprehend firm behaviour and link sustainability practices of firm with the idea of competitive advantage.

4.3.5 Summary of results from business economics theories

Neither one of the regarded theories from business economics nor the combination of them form a comprehensive theory of the firm. Nevertheless, the findings provide insights into firm behaviour and the underlying motivation going significantly beyond the neoclassical firm concept. Although, only the NRBV directly focuses on sustainable relevant behaviour and ways to reduce the negative impacts of firms, the other theories can as well serve as a tool to understand this behaviour. The findings regarding the two guiding questions for this literature review, whether and how the theory pays attention to the sustainability relevance of the firm and whether it can explain sustainable firm behaviour are summarised in the following table. In contrast to the heterodox theories, the business economics theories overall provided more and sounder insight concerning the second question than concerning the first.

	Explanatory power for influence and linkability of firm behaviour on and with sustainability			Triggers for change in firm behaviour
	Ecological Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Economic Sustainability	
Natural-resource-based view	<p>Ecological environment is the source of the competitive advantage</p> <p>Search for strategies to reduce the negative impact of firms and simultaneously improve competitive advantage</p>	<p>Socioeconomic drivers of poverty and inequity and the role of firms are assessed</p> <p>Search for strategies to reduce the negative impact of firms and simultaneously improve competitive advantage</p>	<p>The strategies serve the purpose to improve the competitiveness of firms by growing and thus traditional economic growth</p>	<p>The linkage between ecologically and socially sustainable behaviour with thereby improving the competitive advantage offers a solid explanation for the motivation of firms</p>
Stakeholder theory	<p>Only if environment or nature is seen as a stakeholder on its own or if there are intermediary stakeholders</p>	<p>Firm is dependent on various social actors and influences them</p> <p>Stakeholder management can put them in a better position but only those in the surrounding of the firm</p>	<p>Stakeholder management serves the purpose of improving the competitiveness of firms and therefore traditional economic growth</p>	<p>Sustainable firm behaviour will occur if sustainability is a major stakeholder interest</p>
Corporate social responsibility	<p>CSR measures can aim at the firm's ecological impact, but it is not part of the theory</p>	<p>CSR measures can aim at the firm's social impact, but it is not part of the theory</p>	<p>No direct link but the theory opens the possibility of not-for-profit firm behaviour out of ethical motivation</p>	<p>Firms act sustainably either out of ethical reasons or to gain reputation and to change their image to be the solution of sustainability problems to maintain their needed societal licence to operate</p>
Dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity	<p>The vague concept provides no explicit examination of concrete mutually impacts with the ecological system</p>	<p>The vague concept provides no explicit examination of concrete mutually impacts with the social sphere</p>	<p>A very dynamic understanding of emergence and decay within the economic system</p>	<p>Examines firm behaviour and links sustainability practices of firm with the idea of competitive advantage</p>

Table 4.2: Summary of results from business economics theories

5 Conceptual ideas for teaching

5.1 General aims of a new economic education

To change the economy as a whole, it is not enough that the already presented necessary knowledge about how the economy works and about the need for fundamental change exists. There is already a lot of knowledge about it, yet it is not enough if there are some experts who are fully aware of the situation but, following the thoughts from chapter 3.1, the ideas have to be transmitted to as many people in the economy as possible. All ideas are conceived from the academic literature, so as shown, there is a huge research area concerning these topics and even specialised study programmes exist, but most parts of the economic education do not cover these topics what is shown in chapter 3.2. The aim of a new sustainability-sensitive economic education can no longer focus on a small share of students who want to concentrate on these topics,¹⁵ but has to reach all economics and business students who will in the future occupy positions that shape the economic system such as researchers and teachers but also managers, business journalists, and government officials.

Because of these considerations, the alternative ideas for teaching economics that this thesis wants to elaborate are meant to be used in a basic, at best mandatory, course, such as an introduction to economics for all students to amplify the impact. The fact that most students only take a few courses in economics that shape their understanding of the economy poses a challenge because the time for teaching the relevant ideas is very limited. Yet, the lecture could of course ideally be supplemented with related courses such as economic history, political science or philosophy to provide contextual knowledge about the economic system.

All this has the aim to broaden the awareness of understanding the economy, sustainability issues within the economy and to “develop individuals with knowledge and skills to make decisions based on their environmental, social and economic context, through reflection and critical thinking, so that students are oriented toward action and change” (Figueiró et al. 2016, p. 1). The aim is to return the big questions to the economics syllabus, which includes sustainability questions, and to offer a more problem-centred teaching to students (Ötsch and Kapeller 2010).

There are some notable publications and works with related aims, which is shown in Table 5.1 and sorted by relevance for this chapter. This literature can be classified in two groups: one is about ways to integrate sustainability into economic or business education¹⁶ and the other about teaching heterodox economics. However, there is no work done yet about the combination, about teaching and integrating sustainability via heterodox approaches in economics. This gap is what this thesis wants to draw attention to and give pathways, ideas and suggestions for further development in the following chapters.

¹⁵ Lee (2005) for example focuses explicitly on conceptualising courses and content for a special heterodox graduate programme.

¹⁶ Indeed Christensen et al. (2007) found a strong trend towards increased inclusion of sustainability related courses at the Financial Times top 50 global MBA programmes.

Sustainability in economics and business education	
Figueiró et al. (2016)	The use of social learning (conducting social projects with students) for teaching sustainability issues at business schools
Benn and Dunphy (2009)	Integrating sustainability into MBA programs
Lourenço (2013)	Teaching sustainable development in business schools
Springett (2005)	Critical thoughts about education for sustainability in the business studies curriculum
Stubbs and Cocklin (2008)	Teaching different perspectives of sustainability to business students
Thomas (2005)	Framework of measuring the effects of teaching sustainability in business schools on students
Gray (2013)	Interaction and integration between sustainability and accounting and finance with example of an undergraduate course

Heterodox economics education	
Stilwell (2011)	Ways to teach a pluralistic course in economics and gives experiences from the University of Sydney
Earl and Wakeley (2005)	Teaching heterodox microeconomics to introductory students
Lee (2005)	General ways and syllabi of teaching heterodox microeconomics

Table 5.1: Literature on teaching sustainability and heterodox economics

5.2 Framework for teaching concept and own experiences

As a foundation for this conceptual chapter with the aim to draw up a framework for further development of teaching sustainability-sensitive firm theory with the help of heterodox and business economics, the framework and experiences of an introductory course on microeconomics taught at the University of Kassel in the summer term 2017 will be used as a case study.¹⁷ The author of this thesis contributed during conceptualisation and execution of the course as a teaching assistant to Frank Beckenbach who coordinated the course.

The overall idea of this experiment was to teach microeconomics in a more pluralistic way, compared to the standard version that is usually taught to Bachelor's students (see chapter 3.2), with a twofold approach. First, the views of different heterodox economic schools of thought were integrated in the syllabus in addition to the mainstream economic models and second, the

¹⁷A like-mindedly conceptualised framework for integrating sustainability into the architectural higher education can be found at Hassanpour et al. (2017).

method of teaching was more pluralistic by offering a workshop-like lecture in addition to the weekly lectures and tutorials. In these workshops, the content of the lecture was made more accessible, experienceable and applicable for the students by conducting group work, case studies, economic experiments¹⁸, and discussions. Both, the pluralistic content and the pluralistic teaching should allow the students to gain a broader and more comprehensive understanding of microeconomic actors and economic interrelationships than the neoclassical approach.

The syllabus consisted of three chapters, following a traditional structure. The first one was about households, the second about firms and the third about markets, which meant that the time dedicated to the characteristics and behaviour of firms consisted of three weeks of the course – and so three one and a half hour lectures and three two and a half hour workshops.

The lecture about firms was split in two parts: starting first with the common neoclassical perspective on the firm and continuing second with giving an evolutionary perspective with the overall notion of goal-oriented behaviour of firms with imperfect rationality and profit-sufficiency and a general scheme and evolutionary models for firm decision-making. Besides that, in the workshops the students developed on their own a broader understanding of what a firm is. In the first session, the students explored the differences between the general schemes of decision-making in firms in a stylised neoclassical and a stylised evolutionary world with the so-called archaeologists' congress method.¹⁹ The second session consisted of an experiment following the idea of Bergstrom and Miller (2000, pp. 191–193). In small groups, the students had to execute in a limited time the foundation of a firm and the development of a prescribed product, a paper plane. At the end of the game the output (quantity and quality of products) was compared at a simulated market to allocate gains and losses to determine which firm performed best in this competitive environment. The aim of the experiment was to show that group (or firm) organisation, coping with imperfect information, division of labour, and the decision on how much time and resources to allocate on research and development and production is key for a superior output. In the last session, the students explored in group work special different heterodox schools of thought such as Marxist, Keynesian, post-Keynesian, feminist, and ecological economics and their understanding of the firm.

Building on this experience, ideas and possibilities how to make the findings from chapter 4 usable for teaching will be sketched in the following chapter. The overall feasibility and possible institutional barriers for changing the economic education will not be assessed in this thesis, but some concrete suggestions will be given on how the chapter about firm theory within an introductory economics course could be build up to incorporate the knowledge from different heterodox – theories in order to tackle the presented shortcomings of the current economic education.

¹⁸ See Bergstrom and Miller (2000) for a compilation of economic classroom experiments.

¹⁹ A description of and remarks on this method can be found at Dallmeier and Hawelka (2009).

5.3 Conceptual ideas for teaching firm theory

Similar to the course described in chapter 5.2, microeconomics can be taught in three big units: households, firms, and markets. The firm-part then can be divided again into three parts. Each part can but does not have to be covered in one session. Furthermore, the course should be accompanied by an open-minded economics textbook. Even if no textbook yet covers the core ideas of this thesis, a textbook as open-minded as possible²⁰ can complement the understanding of the economy.

5.3.1 Part one: What are firms?

The first part is about the question what firms are in general and about their role in the world. This has to start with a historical introduction about the origin and development and about spectrum and activities of firms as well as reasons for having firms in the first place. Altogether this introduction already surpasses the ahistorical neoclassical concept. Here ideas of the theory of production, division of labour, and trade should be introduced. After the historical introduction and definition, the firm can be conceptualised as an embedded entity, which is the core element that students should pick up from this part. The ecological economics model (see Figure 4.3) with firms and households interacting with each other and with the interactions between the economic and human sphere and the ecological sphere can be the starting point for understanding the physical role of the firm. The interactions between firms and households should be understood but also the impact of these interactions on the natural environment. Increased economic activity and a growth of the economy should be seen as both, positive and negative, because it can create value and increase wealth but also environmental degradation. The biophysical view that science shows us that there are at least constraints if not even limits to growth should be generally adopted from the beginning for the understanding of all economic processes.

The social impacts of firms can be understood with a feminist perspective. Here, the social effects of firms and their embeddedness in the society can be discussed. Furthermore, it can be shown that the general aim of the economy and the societal aim of the firm is by no means only money but to serve the society and thus a different view of the firm can be developed.

5.3.2 Part two: What do firms do?

The second part of the course about the firm gives possible answers to the questions what firms do and how this is modulated in economic science. To make firm theory more real-world relatable and accessible for the students, this unit can be started with an inductive rather than a theory-first approach as proposed by Earl and Wakeley (2005). The authors begin their heterodox-oriented microeconomic introduction course by asking their students to read a case study about Richard Branson's early years, when he started building up the Virgin empire. The choice of a useful example depends on country and context. Because most students seem to be familiar with

²⁰ The textbook from Elsner et al. (2014) comes close but there is still a deep lack of open-minded economic textbooks.

Branson, this introduction can, besides motivating the students, serve two goals. First, the example grounds everything that will be developed during the lecture about firm theory in the real world, overcomes the common remoteness of economic theory in the mainstream approach – and thus engages the students better than the mainstream approach. Second, starting with opportunities Branson got, problems he faced, tasks he had to do, and people and institutions his success was dependent on, illustrates the competitive process and automatically leads away from the mainstream assumption of an all-seeing and all-knowing economic agent.

Building on in this example that can be used continuously during the course, a theory of the firm can be developed. Therefore, a comparison of the neoclassical approach and an evolutionary view can be presented. The neoclassical analysis of the firm can be limited to focusing on its assumptions and the idea of a production function or carried out in detail by introducing it geometrically and calculating with numbers the determination of profit maximisation in the firm.

The evolutionary approach can be taught starting with the differing assumptions such as imperfect rationality, learning process and profit sufficiency. Based on the work of Nelson and Winter (1982), a plot of actions happening within the firm can be developed to show the different steps in a firm according to evolutionary theories. With the help of introducing a search algorithm and its function for finding a satisficing profit, the core ideas of evolutionary theory of the firm can be explained. The idea should be complemented with showing and describing simulation process outcomes and results.

This could be even further elaborated with actually using or letting students use and experiment with a real simulation model in class. A Mathematica model based on the model of decision-making under bounded rationality from Wall (1993) can demonstrate how firm behaviour is understood. The firm searches for satisfying solutions instead of exploiting the optimum, which is done with feedback from the surroundings and comparing and learning from the previous periods. Understanding the steps and the local (new solutions emerge as marginal modifications of existing routines), sequential (alternatives are considered one at a time), and experience-driven (learning leads to updating of current routines on the basis of interpretation of previous experience) search within the firm can help the students to understand real world dynamic behaviour of firms as an alternative to the static profit maximisation behaviour of neoclassic models. The evolutionary economic model of Nelson and Winter (1982), moreover, can be used to illustrate processes and interactions of different departments within the firm and the behaviour of firms at a competitive market dealing with other firms. Moreover, the topic of economic stability and instability, economic crises, and the respective role of firms can be touched on here. An outlook for the future of firm theory, especially after the global financial and economic crisis of 2007–2008, and how theory is made in general can be given with presenting some newer heterodox theories of the firm that combine different heterodox approaches such as Jo (2016), Dean (2013), and Lee (2012).

In the final step of this part, a link can be drawn between the firm theories and the topic of the first part, the firm as an embedded entity. The incompatibility of neoclassic models but even more the connectability of evolutionary economics with the embedded view of the firm can be shown with models such as the work of Beckenbach (2001) as an example of how an evolutionary model can integrate ecological and economic changes and the interactions of both.

5.3.3 Part three: Inside the firm and how firms can act for change

The third part of the firm unit zooms into the firm and demonstrates selected processes and drivers for changes in firm behaviour. Therefore, the perspective is changed from the bird's-eye view on the firm to the interior view of the firm and business economics ideas are used.

A discussion about resource-based vs. market-oriented views of the firm can make clear how firms choose their strategies and especially the natural-resource-based view can link this to sustainable firm behaviour.

The concepts of stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility as well as dynamic capabilities and absorptive capacity can be used within the framework of firm theory to explain strategic decisions and triggers for change and, if applicable, to draw connections to other management related subjects the students may attend. With these theories and sustainability-related examples, the students are able to learn how firms can be motivated to reduce their negative and increase their positive impacts on their social and ecological environment, while the general framework developed in the first two parts should not be neglected.

Finally, based on these theories, classroom experiments such as the paper plane experiment from chapter 5.2 can make the theoretical knowledge stick and let the students experience how processes in firms actually work and how far they differ from the neoclassical mainstream models.

6 Conclusion

This thesis is built on three big pillars that it tries to connect: heterodox economic theory of the firm, sustainable development, and teaching. The course of the thesis gives an overview of different discussions and develops possible pathways to improve the economic education by better integrating sustainability issues with the help of heterodox economics and business theories in order to serve as a driving force for sustainable development.

Its main idea is derived from recognising that for a sustainable survival of humankind a sustainable economy is needed and that for a change from the current state to a more sustainable economy education is one of the key drivers. For this, the possibilities of education as a driver for development and especially sustainable development are evaluated, the prominent impacts of firms in the capitalist economies on the environmental and human sphere are assessed and their resulting key role for any development of the economic sector is demonstrated. After recalling the major shortcomings of the current mainstream economics, the specific incompatibility of mainstream economic education for the endeavour to understand pressing sustainability issues and thus the need for a paradigm shift is explained.

The core part of the work shows with the example of firm behaviour how heterodox economic theories instead of neoclassic mainstream explanations can not only improve the validity of economic models but also enhance the understanding of the role of firms for sustainable development and the understanding of sustainability as a guiding criterion for firm behaviour. It is apparent that with different heterodox theories the impact of firm behaviour on sustainable development can be significantly better understood than with neoclassical economic models. The variety of approaches that can easily complement each other is evaluated with the traditional but newly defined three dimensions of sustainability.

While ecological economics for example focuses on and explains the impacts of economic activity on ecological systems, feminist and like-minded approaches highlight the impact on society and evolutionary economics can help to understand changes in the economy, crisis phenomena and thus better explain the economic sustainability. Business economics theories, moreover, complement the heterodox approach by opening up the interior of the firm. Concepts derived from business studies such as NRBV, CSR, stakeholder theory, dynamic capability and absorptive capacity have proven to be suitable to understand the multidimensional nature of motives of firms that are in reality much more complex than the simplified economic models.

Clearly, an improved firm theory or an improved economic theory does not automatically lead to a more sustainable firm behaviour or a more sustainable economy – and neither does a better and more sustainability-sensitive economic education. Sustainability and the needed corresponding changes are a normative challenge, but modern, open-minded economics can provide the scientific framework for profoundly understanding the situation, the impacts driven by economic activity on environment, society and economy and the need for and processes of change. Moreover, the thesis shows that such a shared understanding regarding the economy as a stepping stone for sustainable development has to be spread throughout the economy through an appropriate economic education that must differ from its current form. To enable the future generation to make informed normative decisions towards sustainable development, a different economic education is necessary today that opens the eyes for the already existing findings and approaches concerning sustainable development in economics and related fields.

An improved open-minded and sustainability-sensitive economic education can be part of a bigger development towards an improved societal awareness for the meaning of sustainability challenges for today's decisions. Ever since the emergence of economics as a scientific discipline it has not only observed and described but also influenced and catalysed individual and social processes and policy makers have ever since turned to economic frameworks to guide policy. Thus, not only individual decisions in the economy by researchers, managers, business analysts, journalists or government officials that are shaped by their economic education, but also the overall opinion-forming process concerning economic and economic-policy topics – and so the acceptance of ambitious climate, energy, and environment policies – can benefit from a better understanding of the interdependencies between the economic, the ecological, and the human sphere. An open-minded economics that is changed to recognise and understand the respective current and future challenges and that is widely spread through education can develop and act as the decisive vehicle to provide both, new options for action – such as new innovation or environmental policy – and new horizons of meaning and significance – such as new life and social models – for the purpose of overcoming the threats for the existence of humankind and seizing the opportunities for a higher level of societal prosperity and wellbeing.

In this spirit, a concrete exemplary model of a teaching concept for microeconomic firm theory is developed as an outlook on how an economic education that incorporates sustainability issues with the help of heterodox economic theories and business economics might be looking. The concept of using different approaches allows a multi-perspective view on the firm enhancing the understanding of its characteristics, its behaviours, and its role in the physical and social world compared to the current mainstream economic explanations. Rather than a ready-made syllabus, the concept serves to point out pathways of future proceedings and to provide a pool of ideas for teaching sustainability-sensitive firm theory.

Much further work is henceforward needed, first, to elaborate and customise the given firm chapter, second, to develop similar ideas for the other classic microeconomic topics, households and markets, and finally to do the same for all other economic education areas up to macroeconomic and political topics, in order to reform the whole economic syllabus from bottom up. Moreover, the conceptual nature of this work yearns for not only elaborating on the ideas but also analysing practicable ways for and possible barriers to processes of change within a given educational system.

But no matter how small and limited it is, the given example alone shows, with reminiscence to the case study of the previously conducted microeconomic lecture, that a change in the economic education is possible and that it can already be initiated by gradually altering the syllabus. This can be a starting point meaning that everyone who actually is teaching economics in one way or another can support the needed change in economics by opening up the curriculum to some of the provided or similar heterodox ideas and thus help to initiate the development of a more sustainability- and future-oriented economic education for more sustainable economic activity and policy to create a more sustainable economy and a more sustainable world.

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